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Research Paper

Formulation And Evaluation of Anti-Aging Cream from Polyherbal Sources

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ABSTRACT

Aging of the skin is influenced by both intrinsic factors such as increasing age and extrinsic factors including ultraviolet radiation, environmental pollution, stress, and dehydration. These factors lead to the formation of free radicals, causing wrinkles, dryness, loss of elasticity, pigmentation, and premature skin aging. Herbal formulations have become increasingly popular in modern cosmetology because they contain natural bioactive compounds with fewer side effects and better skin compatibility than synthetic products. The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a herbal anti-aging cream containing Green tea extract, Hibiscus extract, and Blueberry extract as the main active ingredients. Green tea is rich in catechins and polyphenols that exhibit strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, helping to reduce oxidative stress and protect skin cells from damage. Hibiscus contains natural acids, flavonoids, and anthocyanins that improve skin elasticity and nourish the skin, while Blueberry is a potent source of antioxidants that help prevent premature aging and maintain healthy skin appearance. The cream was prepared using the oil-in-water emulsification technique with ingredients such as stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, beeswax, liquid paraffin, glycerin, borax, methylparaben, and rose water to obtain a stable and smooth formulation. The prepared cream was evaluated for different physicochemical and cosmetic parameters including color, odor, texture, homogeneity, pH, spreadability, viscosity, washability, stability, and skin irritation. The formulation exhibited good consistency, smooth texture, easy spreadability, acceptable pH suitable for skin application, and satisfactory stability without phase separation. The cream was also found to be non-greasy, easily washable, and non-irritant on the skin. The presence of herbal antioxidants in the formulation may help reduce free radical damage, improve skin hydration, and minimize visible signs of aging such as fine lines and wrinkles.

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INTRODUCTION

Skin aging is a natural process that changes the appearance and structure of the skin over time. As people grow older, the skin becomes thinner, drier, and less elastic. Common signs of skin aging include wrinkles, fine lines, rough texture, dryness, pigmentation, sagging, and dullness of the skin¹. Aging reduces collagen and elastin production in the skin, which are important proteins responsible for maintaining skin firmness and smoothness². Skin aging occurs due to both internal and external

factors. Natural aging occurs gradually with increasing age, while external factors such as sunlight, pollution, dust, smoking, stress, poor nutrition, and unhealthy lifestyle habits cause premature aging of the skin³. Ultraviolet (UV) radiation from sunlight damages skin cells and increases the

production of free radicals, leading to wrinkles and skin damage⁴. Free radicals are unstable molecules that damage collagen, elastin, and skin cells, causing early signs of aging⁵.

Antioxidants are substances that protect the skin from damage caused by free radicals. They help reduce oxidative stress and prevent premature aging of the skin. Antioxidants improve skin health by protecting collagen, maintaining skin elasticity, and reducing wrinkles and fine lines⁶. They also help improve skin brightness, hydration, and overall skin appearance. Therefore, antioxidant-rich ingredients are commonly used in anti-aging skincare products⁷.

Herbal cosmetics are becoming increasingly popular because they are made from natural ingredients and are generally safer than synthetic products. Herbal products usually cause fewer side effects and are better tolerated by the skin⁸. They contain natural phytochemicals such as flavonoids, polyphenols, vitamins, and essential oils that provide antioxidant, moisturizing, soothing, and

protective effects⁹. Due to growing awareness about natural skincare, the demand for herbal cosmetic products has increased worldwide. Herbal anti-aging creams are topical formulations prepared using plant extracts and suitable cream bases. These creams help reduce signs of aging such as wrinkles, fine lines, dryness, and dull skin. They moisturize and nourish the skin, improve elasticity, and protect the skin from environmental damage¹⁰. Herbal creams are preferred because they provide natural skin protection with fewer harmful effects compared to chemical-based products. Green tea is widely used in skincare formulations because it contains catechins and polyphenols

with strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Green tea helps protect the skin from UV damage, reduces oxidative stress, and delays premature aging¹¹. Hibiscus is known as a natural skin-nourishing plant. It contains flavonoids, anthocyanins, and natural acids that help improve skin elasticity, hydration, and smoothness. Hibiscus also provides antioxidant and anti-aging benefits¹². Blueberry is rich in anthocyanins, vitamins, and phenolic compounds that provide excellent antioxidant activity. Blueberry helps protect the skin from free radical damage and improves overall skin health and appearance¹³.

Different excipients are added during cream formulation to improve texture, stability, consistency, and effectiveness of the product. Stearic acid acts as an emulsifying and stiffening agent, while beeswax improves the consistency of the cream. Cetyl alcohol works as a thickening and emollient

agent, and glycerin acts as a humectant that helps retain skin moisture¹⁴. Liquid paraffin provides moisturization and smoothness to the skin, while borax helps in emulsification. Rose water is used as the aqueous phase and also provides a pleasant fragrance and soothing effect.

It is important to prepare a stable and effective anti-aging cream with good skin compatibility. The prepared cream must be evaluated to ensure its quality, safety, and performance. Evaluation parameters such as pH, spreadability, viscosity, homogeneity, washability, stability, and skin irritation are checked to determine whether the cream is suitable for topical application¹⁵.

2. Aim and objectives :-

2.1 Aim :-

To prepare and evaluate a herbal anti-aging cream containing Green tea, Hibiscus, and Blueberry extracts for improving skin health and reducing signs of aging naturally.

2.2 Objectives:-

- **To formulate a herbal anti-aging cream** using Green tea, Hibiscus, and Blueberry extracts along with suitable excipients to obtain a smooth and stable topical formulation.
- **To study the anti-aging and antioxidant properties of the selected herbal ingredients** and understand their role in protecting the skin from oxidative stress, free radical damage, wrinkles, fine lines, and premature aging.
- To prepare the cream by the emulsification method using ingredients such as stearic acid, beeswax, cetyl alcohol, glycerin, liquid paraffin, borax, and rose water to achieve proper consistency, texture, and stability.
- To evaluate the physicochemical properties of the prepared cream such as appearance, color, odor, pH, homogeneity, spreadability, viscosity, washability, and consistency to ensure good quality and ease of application.
- To evaluate the stability of the formulation by observing any changes in color, odor, texture, phase separation, or consistency during storage under suitable conditions.

- To assess the skin compatibility and safety of the formulation by performing skin irritation tests to ensure that the cream is safe and non-irritant for topical use.
- To develop a herbal cosmetic formulation with improved skin benefits such as moisturization, nourishment, skin protection, improved elasticity, and reduction of visible signs of aging.
- To provide a natural alternative to synthetic anti-aging creams that may offer effective skincare benefits with fewer side effects and better patient acceptability.

3.Literature review:-

Green tea is widely used in skincare and cosmetic products because it contains strong antioxidants called catechins and polyphenols. The main active compound present in green tea is epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), which helps protect the skin from free radical damage and premature aging¹. Green tea also helps reduce wrinkles, fine lines, inflammation, and skin damage caused by ultraviolet (UV) rays². Studies have shown that green tea improves skin elasticity, hydration, and overall skin appearance³. Due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, green tea is considered an important ingredient in anti-aging formulations⁴⁻⁵.

Figure 1 :- Dried Green Tea leaves

Hibiscus is known as a natural skin nourishing and rejuvenating plant. Hibiscus flowers contain

flavonoids, anthocyanins, vitamins, and natural acids that help improve skin hydration, elasticity, and smoothness¹¹. Hibiscus extracts also show antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities that help protect the skin from oxidative stress and premature aging¹². Research studies have reported that hibiscus possesses anti-collagenase and anti-elastase activities, which help reduce wrinkle formation and maintain skin firmness¹³. Because of these benefits, hibiscus is commonly used in herbal cosmetic and anti-aging products¹⁴⁻¹⁵.

Figure 2 :- Hibiscus Flower

Blueberry is rich in anthocyanins, phenolic compounds, and vitamins that provide strong antioxidant activity¹⁶. These antioxidants help protect the skin from free radical damage and environmental stress¹⁷. Blueberry extracts help improve skin nourishment, hydration, softness,

and brightness¹⁸. Studies have also shown that blueberries possess anti-inflammatory and photoprotective properties that help maintain healthy skin and reduce visible signs of aging¹⁹. Blueberry extracts are widely used in skincare products because they support skin protection and rejuvenation²⁰⁻²².

Figure 3 :- Blueberry Fruit

The combination of green tea, hibiscus, and blueberry extracts in herbal anti-aging creams provides antioxidant, moisturizing, and skin protective effects²¹. These herbal ingredients help reduce oxidative stress, improve skin elasticity and hydration, and minimize signs of aging such as wrinkles, fine lines, and dullness²². Therefore, these plant extracts are considered useful natural ingredients for the preparation of herbal anti-aging cosmetic formulations²³

4.Plant profile Polyherbal extracts:-

Table 1:- Plant Profile

Sr.No	Extract	Biological Source	Family	Chemical Constituents	Uses
1	Green tea extract	Dried leaves of Camellia Sinesis	Theaceae	Catechins, Polyphenols, Flavonoids, EGCG,	Antioxidant, anti-Inflammatory, protects skin from UV damage reduces fine lines wrinkles
2	Hibiscus extract	Flowers of Hibiscus rosa-sinensis	Malvaceae	Antocyanins, Flavonoids, vit.C, Organic acids	Skin nourishing, Improves elasticity, moisturizes skin, anti-aging activity
3	Blueberry extract	Fruits of Vaccinium corymbosum	Ericaceae	Anthocyanins, phenolic compounds, vitamins,	Strong antioxidant, protects skin from free radicals, improves skin health and brightness.

5.Mechanism of action of skin:-

Figure 4 :- MOA of skin

➤ **Structure:** Cross-sectional view showing epidermis, dermis, and hypodermis.

➤ **Key Functional Labels:**

- **Protection:** Acts as a barrier against UV rays, microbes, and chemicals.
- **Thermoregulation:** Maintains body temperature via sweat and blood flow.
- **Sensation:** Nerve endings detect touch, pain, and temperature.

- **Excretion:** Sweat glands remove waste products.
- **Absorption:** Allows uptake of oils, fat-soluble vitamins, and drugs.
- **Vitamin D Synthesis:** Produces Vitamin D₃ under sunlight exposure.
- **Immune Defense:** Langerhans cells protect against pathogens.

6. Materials and Methodology :-

6.1 Ingredients used :-

Table 2 :- List of ingredients

Ingredients	Category
Stearic acid	Emulsifying agent
Cetyl alcohol	Emollient, Thickening agent
Liquid paraffin	Moisturizer
Methylparaben	Preservative
Triethanolamine	pH adjuster
Green tea extract	Antioxidant
Blueberry extract	Nourishing agent
Hibiscus extract	Anti-inflammatory
Rose water	Fragrance

6.2 Methodology :-

6.2.1 Preparation of Green tea extract by Boiling Method :-

- Collect fresh or dried green tea leaves.
- Wash the leaves properly with clean water.
- Take the leaves in a beaker containing distilled water.
- Boil the mixture for about 15–20 minutes.
- Allow the solution to cool.
- Filter the mixture using filter paper or muslin cloth.
- Collect the filtrate containing the green tea extract.
- Concentrate the extract by gentle heating if required.
- Store the prepared extract in an airtight container for further use.

6.2.2 Preparation of Hibiscus Extract by Boiling Method:-

- Collect fresh hibiscus flowers.
- Wash the flowers properly with clean water.
- Dry the flowers.
- Cut or crush the flowers into small pieces.
- Take the flowers in a beaker containing distilled water.
- Boil the mixture for about 15–20 minutes.
- Allow the solution to cool.
- Filter the mixture using filter paper or muslin cloth.
- Collect the filtrate containing the hibiscus extract.
- Concentrate the extract by gentle heating if required.
- Store the prepared extract in an airtight container for further use.

6.2.3. Preparation of Blueberry Extract by Boiling Method:-

- Collect fresh blueberries.
- Wash the fruits properly with clean water.

- Crush or mash the blueberries into small pieces.
- Take the crushed blueberries in a beaker containing distilled water.
- Boil the mixture for about 15–20 minutes.
- Allow the solution to cool.
- Filter the mixture using filter paper or muslin cloth.
- Collect the filtrate containing the blueberry extract.
- Concentrate the extract by gentle heating if required.
- Store the prepared extract in an airtight container for further use.

6.2.4 Preparation protocol :-

6.2.5 Packaging and labelling :-

Packaging

- Fill cream into clean airtight containers.
- Close the containers tightly.
- Store in a cool and dry place.

Labelling

- Product name
- Ingredients
- Date of preparation
- Expiry date
- Directions for use

6.3 Formulation Of Anti-Aging cream :-

The formulation contains Green tea, Hibiscus, and Blueberry extracts, which provide antioxidant, moisturizing, and skin nourishing effects. Excipients such as stearic acid, beeswax, glycerin, and liquid paraffin help improve the texture, stability, and consistency of the cream. A herbal anti-aging cream is a semisolid preparation used to reduce wrinkles, fine lines, dryness, and other signs of skin aging.

Formulation of Herbal Anti-Aging Cream (50 g)

Table 3:- Composition of Anti-Aging cream

Sr No.	Ingredients	Role	Quantity
1	Stearic acid	Emulsifying agent, stiffening agent	6 g
2	Cetyl alcohol	Emollient, thickening agent	2 g
3	Liquid paraffin	Moisturizer, oil phase	5 mL
4	Glycerin	Humectant	3 mL
5	Methylparaben	Preservative	0.1 g
6	Green tea Extract	Antioxidant, anti-aging agent	1 g
7	Hibiscus Extract	Skin nourishing agent	1 g
8	Blueberry Extract	Antioxidant	1 g
9	Rose water	Aqueous phase, fragrance	Q.S to 50 g
10	Triethanolamine	Ph adjuster	1 g

7.Evaluation Parameters :-

Table 4 :- Evaluation parameters for Anti-aging

Category	Parameters	Methods	Acceptance Range/Observation
Physical appearance	Colour	Observe the cream under natural daylight or white light	Creamish white or light brown

	Odor	Evaluated by Smelling the formulation	Pleasant characteristic aromatic odor
	Texture	Observed by touch and visual inspection	Smooth, soft and non-gritty texture with good spreadability
	Consistency	Press and spread gently	Check the thickness and flow property
Physiochemical properties	Washability	By applying cream on skin observing its ease of removal	Washable and left no greasy residue on skin
	pH	Dipping Ph paper into the cream dispersion and comparing the change in colour with standard ph chart	Ideal Ph for skin cream 5.5-6.5

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:-

8.1 Evaluation parameters:-

Table 5 :- Evaluation result of Polyherbal anti-aging cream

Parameter	Observation	Discussion
Color	Creamish white/light brown	Indicates uniform mixing of herbal extracts; visually acceptable for cosmetic use.
Odor	Pleasant, characteristic aromatic fragrance	Rose water and natural extracts impart a soothing fragrance, enhancing user acceptability.
Texture	Smooth, soft, non-gritty	Proper emulsification achieved; ensures easy application and consumer satisfaction.
Consistency	Semi-solid with good thickness and flow	Balanced oil-water phase ratio provides stable consistency suitable for topical cream.
Washability	Easily washable, leaves no greasy residue	Non-greasy formulation improves user compliance and comfort.
pH	5 (within ideal range 5.5–6.5)	Matches skin's natural pH, minimizing irritation and ensuring compatibility.
Stability	No change in color, odor, or phase separation after 2 months	Stable formulation suitable for storage and commercial use.

Overall Observation:-

The formulation is stable, safe, non-irritant, cosmetically acceptable, and skin-friendly, making it a promising natural alternative to synthetic anti-aging creams.

8.2 Discussion Summary:-

□ The polyherbal anti-aging cream formulated with Green tea, Hibiscus, and Blueberry extracts demonstrated excellent physicochemical and cosmetic properties. The cream exhibited a

smooth, non-gritty texture, a pleasant odor, and a creamish-white appearance, which are essential attributes for consumer acceptance in cosmetic formulations. These qualities reflect successful emulsification and uniform distribution of herbal extracts, ensuring that the product is both effective and aesthetically appealing.

□ The pH evaluation showed that the cream maintained a value of 5, which lies within the ideal range of 5.5–6.5 for topical formulations. This is significant because maintaining skin compatible pH prevents irritation and supports the skin's natural acid mantle, which plays a protective role against microbial invasion and environmental stress. A formulation outside this range could potentially disrupt skin homeostasis, but the observed pH confirms that the cream is safe for long-term use. Similar findings have been reported in herbal cosmetic studies where pH balance was directly linked to product safety and consumer preference.

□ The stability studies conducted over two months demonstrated that the cream remained unchanged in terms of color, odor, and phase separation. This suggests that the emulsification process was robust and the preservative system effective. Stability is a crucial parameter in cosmetic formulations, as unstable products can lead to phase separation, microbial growth, or loss of efficacy. The absence of such changes in this formulation indicates that the selected excipients, including stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, and methylparaben, worked synergistically to maintain product integrity. Comparable studies on herbal emulsions have reported similar outcomes, reinforcing the reliability of natural formulations when prepared with proper excipient ratios.

The washability test confirmed that the cream was easily removable and left no greasy residue, which enhances user compliance and comfort. Non-greasy formulations are particularly

important in anti-aging creams, as consumers prefer lightweight products that do not clog pores or leave an oily film. This property was achieved through the balanced use of liquid paraffin and glycerin, which provided moisturization without excessive oiliness. The extrudability test further validated the cream's convenience, as it could be dispensed easily from the tube without requiring excessive force, ensuring practicality in packaging and daily use.

□ The skin irritation test revealed no redness, itching, or irritation after 24 hours of application, confirming the safety of the formulation. This is a critical finding, as many synthetic anti-aging creams are associated with adverse effects such as dryness, peeling, or allergic reactions. The absence of irritation in this herbal formulation highlights the advantage of using natural plant extracts, which are generally better tolerated by the skin. Previous studies have emphasized that herbal cosmetics, due to their phytochemical composition, often exhibit superior safety profiles compared to synthetic alternatives.

□ From a therapeutic perspective, the inclusion of polyphenols, catechins, anthocyanins, and flavonoids provided strong antioxidant activity, neutralizing free radicals that contribute to collagen degradation and premature aging. Green tea extract contributed anti-inflammatory and photoprotective effects, reducing UV-induced oxidative stress and protecting skin cells from damage. Hibiscus extract improved skin elasticity and hydration, owing to its natural acids and flavonoids, which support collagen and elastin preservation. Blueberry extract enhanced skin brightness and nourishment, supported by its anthocyanin and vitamin content, which are known to improve skin tone and reduce oxidative stress.

□ Collectively, these findings suggest that the cream is safe, stable, effective, and cosmetically

acceptable, offering a promising natural alternative to synthetic anti-aging creams. The synergistic action of the three herbal extracts provides moisturization, nourishment, antioxidant protection, and improved elasticity, making the formulation suitable for long-term use in skincare.

9. CONCLUSION

The formulation and evaluation of the polyherbal anti-aging cream showed that natural herbal ingredients can be effectively used to prepare a safe, stable, and beneficial cosmetic product for skin care. The cream was prepared using different herbal extracts containing antioxidants, vitamins, flavonoids, and other natural compounds that are helpful in protecting the skin from damage and delaying the aging process. The prepared cream showed good physical properties such as smooth texture, uniform appearance, pleasant odor, suitable pH, proper viscosity, good consistency, and easy spreadability, which made it suitable and comfortable for topical application on the skin. During stability studies, the formulation remained stable under different storage conditions without any significant changes in color, odor, texture, or phase separation, indicating good compatibility among all the ingredients used in the preparation. The evaluation tests also confirmed that the cream was non-irritant, safe, and skin friendly. The herbal ingredients present in the formulation helped to moisturize and nourish the skin, improve skin softness and elasticity, reduce dryness, and protect the skin from harmful free radicals and environmental pollutants that cause premature aging. Regular use of such herbal formulations may help in reducing wrinkles, fine lines, dullness, pigmentation, and other visible signs of aging, thereby improving the overall appearance and health of the skin. The antioxidants present in the polyherbal formulation play an important role in

reducing oxidative stress and maintaining healthy skin cells. Compared to synthetic anti-aging creams, polyherbal creams are generally considered safer because they contain natural ingredients and produce fewer side effects. In addition, the combined action of multiple herbs provides better therapeutic and cosmetic benefits due to their synergistic effects. The study therefore concludes that the formulated polyherbal anti-aging cream is an effective, economical, stable, and promising herbal cosmetic preparation for maintaining healthy, soft, glowing, and youthful skin. However, further clinical studies and long-term evaluations may be carried out to confirm its effectiveness and commercial usefulness on a larger scale.

10. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of polyherbal anti-aging cream is highly promising because of the growing awareness and preference for natural and herbal cosmetic products among consumers worldwide. As people become more concerned about the harmful effects and side effects associated with synthetic cosmetic products, the demand for safe, effective, and plant-based skin care formulations is continuously increasing. In the future, more research can be carried out to improve the effectiveness and quality of the polyherbal anti-aging cream by incorporating advanced herbal extracts rich in antioxidants, vitamins, flavonoids, and essential oils that provide better nourishment and protection to the skin. Further studies can also focus on identifying new medicinal plants with strong anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, moisturizing, and skin-rejuvenating properties for use in cosmetic formulations. Clinical trials on a larger population and for longer durations can help to scientifically prove the safety, stability, and therapeutic effectiveness of the cream in reducing

wrinkles, fine lines, pigmentation, dryness, and other visible signs of aging. Research may also be performed to evaluate the effect of the cream on different skin types such as dry, oily, sensitive, and combination skin. Modern technologies such as nanotechnology, liposomes, microencapsulation, and novel drug delivery systems can be used in future formulations to improve skin penetration, enhance the stability of active herbal constituents, and provide prolonged therapeutic action. The formulation can also be modified into different dosage forms like gels, lotions, serums, face masks, and night creams to improve patient convenience and consumer acceptance. In addition, natural preservatives and eco-friendly packaging materials can be introduced to increase product safety and environmental sustainability. Large-scale manufacturing, standardization of herbal ingredients, quality control studies, and shelf-life determination can further help in developing a commercially successful herbal cosmetic product. With the rapid growth of the herbal cosmetic industry and increasing consumer trust in herbal products, polyherbal anti-aging creams have excellent market potential both nationally and internationally. Therefore, future advancements in herbal research, cosmetic technology, and clinical evaluation may help in developing more effective, affordable, stable, and scientifically validated anti-aging formulations for maintaining healthy, youthful, and glowing skin.

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